

A Discussion on Organizational Resilience in Iranian Restaurants During COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Keywords:

Organizational resilience, Iran, hospitality industry, restaurant industry, crisis management, Covid-19 pandemic.

Small and medium-sized businesses were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic and suffered losses in Iran as well as across the globe. An organization's capacity for endurance and tolerance during a crisis is characterized as organizational resilience (OR). In this study, the organizational resilience of restaurants in Iran is evaluated via the lens of OR related dimensions measured by a survey adapted from HealthCheck a free self-assessment tool provided by the Department of Home Affairs of Australia's Organizational Resilience web site. Due to the limitations of time and resources to develop a proper scale, the study confined itself to interpret the descriptive statistical data about the following OR dimensions: decision-making, network and social capital, situational awareness and employee engagement. Analysis indicates a lack of awareness of crisis management and basic management components, and an overall lack of knowledge among managers and employees in terms of risk and crisis management, which is assumed to be a reason for minimal premonition at the onset and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Respondents (restaurant managers/owners) of the survey placed emphasis on the clear hierarchy and efficient decision-making within the organizations as vital parameters.

İran Restoran Sektörü ve Covid-19 Pandemisi Bağlamında Örgütsel Dayanıklılık üzerine Bir Tartışma

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

örgütsel dayanıklılık, İran, restoran sektörü, kriz yönetimi, konaklama işletmeleri,

İşletmelerin kriz sırasındaki dayanıklılık ve tahammül kapasitesi, örgütsel dayanıklılık (ÖD) olarak nitelendirilir. Bu çalışmada, İran'daki restoranların Covid-19 pandemisi sırasındaki örgütsel dayanıklılığı, Avustralya İçişleri Bakanlığı'nun ÖD web sitesinin sağladığı bir öz-değerlendirme aracı olan HealthCheck'ten uyarlanan bir anket aracılığıyla değerlendirilmektedir. Kaynak ve örneklem sınırlamaları nedeniyle çalışmada, şu ÖD boyutlarına ilişkin betimleyici istatistiksel veriler yorumlanmıştır: karar verme, ağ ve sosyal sermaye, durumsal farkındalık ve çalışan katılımı. Analiz, kriz yönetimi ve ilgili yönetim gereksinimleri konusunda farkındalık ve yöneticiler ile çalışanlar arasında risk ve kriz yönetimi açısından genel bilgi eksikliğine işaret etmiştir; bu durumun, pandemi başlangıcında ve sırasında minimum düzeyde önsezinin görülmesinin bir nedeni olduğu düşünülmektedir. Katılanlar (restoran yöneticileri /sahipleri), önemli parametreler olarak kuruluşlar içinde etkin karar verme ilgili olarak hiyerarşinin açık olmasına vurgu yapmıştır.

INTRODUCTION

Iran suffered a lot from COVID-19, which infected over 7 million and killed over 140,000 people by March 2022 (*World Health Org., 2022*). COVID-19 affected many industries, but Iran's food and restaurant industry was not well-studied. This research studied how Iranian restaurants coped with the crisis, using organizational resilience as the main concept. The researcher had a background in tourism and food and collected data from 52 restaurants in three different cities in Iran.

The Research Problem and the Purpose of the Research

Restaurants are an important part of the service and tourism industry, with many workers in them. COVID-19 has hurt the restaurant sector badly, as governments have forced them to close or reduce their capacity. Even after the restrictions are eased, people are still afraid and avoid eating out. (*Li et al. 2021*). This study wants to see how resilient Iranian restaurants are and how they deal with the pandemic. Many restaurants and bars face permanent closure and job losses because of the lockdowns and low demand. (*Nicola et al., 2020, as cited in Neise et al. 2021*). Many trips and vacations in Iran were cancelled because of the quarantine, which also harmed the tourism industry. Many travel companies, hotels and restaurants were affected by this crisis.

Significance of the Research

This research addresses the lack of attention towards the resilience of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the food service industry during crises. The global food service market, valued at \$3.5 trillion in 2020, is projected to grow to \$4.2 trillion by 2027. (*Lock, 2021, as cited in Li et al. 2021*). Organizational resilience (OR), a facet of business continuity management (BCM), is crucial for the industry's ability to endure and recover from crises. Resilience, similar to its meaning in physics, refers to an organization's capacity to withstand challenges while maintaining its function. This study particularly focuses on SMEs due to their vulnerability during crises, lack of resources to counteract impacts. OR is chosen as the primary criterion due to its simplicity, fitting well with SMEs. Data was gathered in 2022 from 52 restaurants in Tehran, Isfahan, and Ahwaz, representing different parts of Iran. These cities were selected based on their geographic diversity and market scale. Convenience and snowball sampling techniques were employed to select the restaurants. Resilience in physics and engineering refers to a material's ability to absorb energy without deforming or to handle stress and disruptions while maintaining form, strength, and function (*Tengblad 2017*). Given the significance of resilience, particularly in the wake of the economic crisis, the concept of "resilience" is also currently being discussed extensively in the literature with reference to small and medium-sized firms. (*Aleksic, Stefanovic, Arsovski and Tadic, 2013; Pal, Torstensson and Mattila, 2014, as cited in Kantur 2015*).

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter delves into crisis management, business continuity management (BCM), and organizational resilience (OR), primarily within the context of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and the hospitality industry, with a specific focus on restaurants. It begins by exploring crisis management and BCM, then shifts to discussing crises within the industry and SMEs. The central emphasis lies on organizational resilience, covering its historical evolution and theoretical as well as practical aspects.

The Concept of Crisis and Crises in the Hospitality and Restaurant Industry

Crises impact both stable and unstable systems, with various definitions. Harvard defines a crisis as a sudden transformative problem (*Harvard Business Review 2015*), while another perspective sees it as an unexpected event endangering stakeholders' expectations. (*Coombs, 2019, p3, as cited in Wut, Xu, and Wong 2021*).

Crises are undesirable, unforeseen, and challenging situations that can fall under different categories, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. (Boin, Kofman & Overdijk, 2004, as cited in Semerciöz et al. 2015). Crises can be divided into various categories, indicating that this research on the COVID pandemic crisis can fall under one of these categories.

Studying restaurant sector strategies is vital due to its integration into the economy. (Li et al. 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic heavily affected restaurants, especially those relying on in-person service. The global drop in restaurant reservations and on-site consumption in March reached 100% compared to the same phase in 2019 in different countries (OpenTable, 2020, as cited Hakim et al. 2021). The restaurant industry is seen as having a pervasive, high level of business risk when seen in the context of the hospitality industry. (Singal, 2012, as cited in Song, Yeon, and Lee 2021) which has worsened during the pandemic. The industry is divided into quick-service, fast-casual, and full-service segments, (Yost et al. 2021) all covered in this research.

The hospitality industry, which includes restaurants, is vulnerable due to its human-dependent, service-oriented nature. (Lovelock et al., 2001, as cited in Patel, J., Kulkarni, V, 2020). The hospitality industry includes restaurants, hotels, bars, pubs, motels, accommodation, food services, etc. Even prior to the outbreak of COVID-19, the hospitality industry had several problems. It is characterized by low pay, long working hours, inadequate working conditions, high turnover, etc. The employees in the hotel sector are mostly temporary and part-time, therefore it is very difficult to survive in any type of crisis. The industry is also facing recruitment and training problems (Patel, J., Kulkarni, V 2020). Even before the pandemic, it faced challenges like low pay and turnover. COVID-19 regulations like social distancing contradicted its essence, causing a significant impact, including a 47% sales drop and widespread layoffs. (National Restaurant Association, 2020, as cited in Song, Yeon, and Lee 2021). The pandemic led to shutdowns, layoffs, and shifts to takeout/delivery services. This evolving situation continues to reshape business hours and operations.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) play a vital role in economies, especially in developing countries. They make up around 90% of businesses globally and contribute over 50% of total jobs. In developing nations, formal SMEs account for up to 40% of the GDP, even more, when considering informal ones. The projected demand for 600 million jobs by 2030 underlines the importance of SME growth for managing the growing workforce. In emerging markets, SMEs create 7 out of 10 new formal jobs. However, limited access to funding remains a major hurdle for SME expansion, despite being the second most common reason hindering their growth in these regions. (<https://www.worldbank.org> 2022).

Smaller businesses are more susceptible to challenges due to their limited resources and family-oriented structure. The hospitality sector, hit hardest by lockdowns, suffered from reduced tourism, impacting both domestic and international travel. Among them, SMEs were particularly affected due to their size, resource constraints, and financial limitations. (Burhan et al. 2021). These groups are vital for economic growth and employment, working alongside governments and related entities. In Iran, such organizations have grown across industries. Recognizing their workforce impact, emerging economies are now adopting varied strategies to enhance SME capabilities and sustainability (Zonouzi et al. 2021). In Iran, the restaurant sector has grown extensively across most cities, unlike other service industries such as tourism. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are widespread in sectors like hospitality, food services, retail, leisure, and manufacturing, which face societal and economic constraints (McKinsey and Company, 2020, As cited in Burhan et al. 2021).

Crisis Management and Business Continuity Management

Studying crisis and its management involves tackling diverse viewpoints, leading to confusion. The field covers numerous aspects: business continuity planning, crisis management, recovery, incident and emergency response, risk and crisis avoidance, and preparedness. Yet, the key challenge isn't just defining these terms. The real risk lies in entrusting business continuity management (BCM) without proactive crisis handling. It's crucial for companies to address crises promptly (Jaques 2018). The challenge in dealing with a crisis stems from aspects tied to organizational and business management – before, during, and after the crisis. In this study, we explore theoretical concepts aimed at reducing confusion and misconceptions across different management areas. Our approach to this literature review is outlined in Figure 1:

Figure 1. From crisis management to organizational resilience

BCM originally comes from the practice and theory of crisis management. It also can be mentioned that it somehow has its origins in contingency planning and disaster recovery planning (Herbane 2010). Before diving into this concept, it should be mentioned that BCM is a holistic management process which means that all the processes related to the organization and its environments and threats are taken into consideration (Crask 2021). A holistic management practice that recognizes probable effects that endanger an organization and delivers a context for building resilience with the capacity for an efficient response that shields the concerns of its significant stakeholders, status, brand and value-creating endeavours (BCMPEDIA. 2008). Effective program management involves training, rehearsals, and reviews to maintain an updated plan. Business Continuity Management (BCM) oversees this comprehensive process to ensure strategic, tactical, and operational responses are prepared for unforeseen events. BCM consists of two main stages: Disaster Recovery Plan and Business Continuity Plan (BCP), with BCP being the central focus (Speight 2011). According to the BCM guidebook developed by the International Labour Organization (ILO) (2011) for SMEs, BCM involves three elements: 1) “preventative measures”; 2) “preparedness arrangements”; and 3) “response options”. Furthermore, all these standards have been established by governmental and non-governmental agencies and institutes to provide and maintain the continuity of the BCM in organizations. For better understanding and giving a clear perspective this research has used the (Wong et al., 2010) discussion and approach. BCM involves three stages: Integration (strategic, HR, and financial aspects), Coordination (business goals, philosophy, strategic understanding), and Recovery. Risk management, BCM, and crisis management functions require different approaches and skills and have different objectives. Moreover, using all of them as an umbrella term would be misleading for an organization (Taber 2017). BCM and crisis management are intertwined, with BCM using crisis management in its continuity plan, notably in the BCP stage. BCP serves as the merging point. The BCM program involves Business Impact Analysis (BIA), financial support, strategic resource implementation, and testing for system verification. OR has emerged as a key idea in the literature on disaster management (McManus, Seville, Vargo, & Brunsdon, 2008, As cited in Orchiston, Prayag, and Brown 2016). Businesses must consider their external environment alongside their internal dynamics. This includes factors like unexpected crises and sector-related changes, such as shifts in regulations. Companies that succeed are skilled at identifying the need for change and updating their strategy to manage unfavourable circumstances in order to lessen the impact on the firm (Carden, Maldonado, and Boyd 2018).

The term "resilience" is addressed in the literature on organizational theory in relation to crisis management, disaster management, high-reliability organizations, and constructive organizational studies (Weick, 1993; Weick, Sutcliffe and Obstfeld, 1999; Tierney, 2003; Paton and Johnson, 2001, as cited in Kantur 2015). In addition to the literature on crisis and disaster management, the term "organizational resilience" began to be used by various authors in the field of organizational studies due to the increased ambiguity and unpredictability in the external competitive, political, and social situations (Doe, 1994; Horne, 1997; Horne and Orr, 1998; Mallak, 1998; Mallak 1999). According to the studies, organizational resilience is primarily understood as an

organization's ability to tolerate adverse and stressful circumstances, as well as its power to hold onto its position and gain from adverse circumstances (*Kantur 2015*).

Organizational Resilience (OR)

Eleven academic sources have been reviewed in order to demonstrate the theoretical definition and progress of the development of the theory of organizational resilience (OR). These are: (*Bruneau, Chang, Eguchi, Lee, O'Rourke, A. M. Reinhorn, et al. 2003*), (*Home and J. Orr 1997*), (*Kantur 2015*), (*Lee, J. J. Vargo, and Seville 2013*), (*Mallak 1998*), (*Neise et al. 2021*), (*Orchiston, Prayag, and Brown 2016*), (*Rose 2006*), (*Weick 1993*), (*Wicker et al. 2013*) and HealthCheck assessment tool from web site of Dept. of Home Affairs of Australian government.

OR, introduced by Weick in 1993, stems from the 1949 Mann Gulch wildfire disaster. It explored organizational resilience, dissecting the fire incident to extract lessons for greater preparedness. Conclusions highlighted improvisation, virtual role systems, wise attitude, and respectful interaction. Bricolage involves crafting solutions from available resources. Wisdom integrates experience, curiosity, and diverse knowledge sources.

Mallak (1998), who used this model in his study defined Weick's model indicators as: The virtual role system (VRS), which indicates an innovative method of work crew interactions (*Mallak 1998*). Mallak's study adds more insights. Communication is vital in crisis management. Hierarchical interactions and role divisions enhance resilience. Effective leadership is crucial for crisis response and formation building.

Home and J. Orr (1997) present a practical approach to organizational resilience. They view OR as a valuable theory, assuming constant evolving changes. They illustrate resilience generation through seven key behaviors: community, competence, connections, commitment, communication, coordination, and consideration.

Mallak (1998) defines resilience as perceiving and adapting to change and stress. His healthcare study expanded Weick's model into six factors: goal-directed solutions, avoidance, critical understanding, role dependence, source reliance, and resource access. These factors encompass problem-solving, skepticism, intelligence application, teamwork, diverse sources, and resourceful access.

According to (*Bruneau, Chang, Eguchi, Lee, O'Rourke, A. M. Reinhorn, et al. 2003*), the concept of resilience is utilized in studies across a variety of fields, including environmental exploration, materials and materials engineering, psychology, sociology, and economics. Resilience denotes toughness and adaptability. The study suggests a multi-measurement approach for performance, expanding the concept. It covers shock prevention, absorption, and rapid recovery. Resilience is gauged by robustness, redundancy, resourcefulness, and speed. Bruno et al. categorize resilience into preventing failure, minimizing impact, and speeding recovery. The study centers on disaster mitigation, emphasizing community involvement, incentives, and enhanced disaster resistance. Study in the hazards field has also increasingly highlighted strategies needed to make communities disaster resistant while addressing long-term issues of sustainability and quality of life, application of intentional practices or mandatory strategies pointed at lessening the significance of an earthquake, along with preparation and readiness actions to improve the efficacy of emergency response immediately after a seismic event, all contributing (*Bruneau, Chang, Eguchi, Lee, O'Rourke, A. M. Reinhorn, et al. 2003*).

Rose, (2006) first provides a definition of "organizational resilience" from the perspectives of engineering, ecology, and organizational behavior. Comparing his work to the other research mentioned above, he places more emphasis on behavioral and economic resilience. Similarly, to that, this is a risk management tactic that falls under the category of crisis and continuity management (*Rose 2006*). Organizational behavior (also institutional) concentrates on resistance as a method (*Hill and Patton, 2005, as cited in Rose 2006*). the ability of people and systems to support healthy relationships even in the presence of serious disorders because of their capacity to attract resources and competencies to complete demands, difficulties, and changes (*Paton, 2001, as cited in Rose 2006*) has been also defined as organizational behavior resilience. The study introduces economic resilience, addressing static and dynamic resistance. These terms connect to short-term and long-term economic concepts. In the short term, certain inputs like capital and equipment remain fixed, while all inputs are variable in the long term. Variable inputs include labor, natural resources, and intermediary products.

Due to the difficulty in expanding inputs, including work or materials, all inputs may be maintained at a constant level in the short term. Static resistance status when we make the best use of currently available inputs (Rose 2006). The study also discusses microeconomic resilience, encompassing markets and businesses. Within this, business resilience has two aspects. Customer resilience focuses on maximizing existing resources during input disruptions, primarily as static resistance. Contrarily, the supply is more resilient and can incorporate system growth (a type of static resistance) in relation to consumer output, although this typically necessitates the building or repair of vital inputs (i.e., dynamic resistance) (Rose 2006). The study suggests eight actions to evaluate business resilience, including resource substitution, import substitution, conservation, inventories, resource importance, and production rescheduling.

Lee, J. J. Vargo, and Seville (2013) defines resilience as a multidimensional phenomenon, addressing managing people during uncertainty. Their study highlights four evaluation standards: linking resilience to competitiveness, economic justification, using leading indicators, and focusing on situational awareness, management, and adaptive capacity. They build upon McManus's (2008) ROR model, updating it to include situational awareness, management, and adaptive capacity. Their new resilience model consists of two main components—planning and adaptive capacity—along with 13 indicators encompassing aspects like resource management, staff engagement, leadership, innovation, and recovery priorities.

Wicker et al. (2013) defines organizational resilience with three dimensions: situational awareness, keystone vulnerabilities management, and adaptive capacity. They use Bruneau et al.'s (2003) concepts of robustness, redundancy, resourcefulness, and rapidity to study affected sports clubs in Australia. They expand community resilience, stating a resilient system should reduce failure chances, consequences, and recovery time. Robustness is the ability to withstand stress, redundancy is replaceability, resourcefulness is problem-solving, and rapidity is timely goal achievement.

In the study by Bruneau, Chang, Eguchi, Lee, O'Rourke, A. M. Reinhorn, et al. (2003), resources, especially human resources and mobilization, were found crucial for organizational and community resilience. Kantur (2015) also used this scale to study organizational resilience amid resource constraints. The term "organizational resilience" is widely accepted but progress, particularly in qualitative and theoretical studies, is slow. Kantur (2015) developed a scale with three factors—Robustness, Agility, and Integrity—measured through 12 survey questions. Robustness assesses resistance, Agility evaluates adaptability, and Integrity gauges employee cohesion within the business.

In a recent study by Neise et al. (2021), the focus was on the restaurant industry in Germany. Organizational resilience was defined as comprising absorption, coping, and adaptation. Neise et al. developed a model with three variables: Problems before COVID-19, Response during COVID-19, and owner/enterprise characteristics, based on Bruneau, Chang, Eguchi, Lee, O'Rourke, A. M. Reinhorn, et al.'s model. The findings indicated that businesses with weak pre-COVID-19 financial standings were less resilient. Financial strength and experienced management were critical resilience factors. Corporate-owned bars and restaurants showed higher resilience, possibly due to better resources and expertise. Businesses facing ongoing structural change were less likely to be perceived as resilient during COVID-19. This suggests local owner-managed businesses were more affected compared to system restaurants and franchises.

Orchiston, Prayag, and Brown (2016) examined tourism and hospitality resilience through earthquake-affected hotels and resorts. They used a Likert scale survey based on Lee et al.'s model with 13 indicators, similar to this study's questionnaire. The findings offer insights for evaluating tourism sector resilience, highlighting planning, culture, collaboration, and innovation. These elements stress the importance of culture, cooperation, and innovation as key to the tourism sector's success. Human capital's significance for reef tourism's resilience aligns with innovation, collaboration, and culture. Table 1 summarizes OR's concept and theory, encompassing definitions and main dimensions.

Table 1. A comparison of organizational resilience (OR) theories

STUDY	YEAR	FEATURES/DIMENSIONS
WEICK	1993	four dimensions of resilience as: "improvisation and bricolage, virtual role system, the attitude of wisdom and respectful interaction"
MALLAK	1997	6 factors model: goal-directed solution-seeking, avoidance, critical understanding, role dependence, source reliance and resource access.
HOME & ORR	1997	7 main streams consist of: "community, competence, connections, commitment, communication, coordination, and consideration".
BRUNEAU ET AL.	2003	"Robustness, Redundancy, Resourcefulness and Rapidity"
ROSE	2006	"Inherent Resource Substitution, Adaptive Resource Substitution, Inherent Import Substitution, Adaptive Import Substitution, Adaptive Conservation, Resource Inventories, Resource Importance and Production Rescheduling".
LEE ET AL	2013	2 main factors and 13 indicators. The two main factors are "planning, and adaptive capacity and the 13 indicators are Minimization of silos, Internal resources, Staff engagement and involvement, Information and knowledge, Leadership, Innovation and creativity, Decision making, Situation monitoring and reporting, Planning strategies, Participation in exercises, Proactive posture, External resources, and Recovery priorities".
WICKER ET AL	2013	"Robustness, redundancy, resourcefulness, and rapidity"
KANTUR	2015	"Robustness, Agility, and Integrity"

OR in BCM Literature and HealthCheck

OR is also recommended in BCM literature. Different terms are used to define OR. Resilience is the term used to describe a body's ability to regain its original form and shape following deformation. The ability to recover from misfortune and move forward stronger than ever is also called resilience (MSB, 2013, as cited in Tengblad, 2017). This study considers organizational, economic, and social perspectives to examine resilience. Organizational Resilience (OR) involves crisis managers making decisions to prevent or reduce the impact of crises. Economic resilience deals with covering crisis-related costs, while social resilience minimizes crisis impact. The research's theoretical model views resilience as an indicator of organizational health. It employs the Organizational Resilience HealthCheck, which is a free self-assessment tool developed by the Department of Home Affairs of Australia's Organizational Resilience website, to gauge adaptability to global markets and address short-term shocks and long-term issues. (<https://www.homeaffairs.gov.au/> 2022). The model incorporates 13 indicators grouped into three attributes: "Leadership and Culture," "Networks," and "Change Ready." Leadership and culture encompass dimensions like Leadership, employee engagement, Situation Awareness, decision-making, and innovation. The OR concept revolves around three traits fostering Business as Usual (BAU), facilitating robust response and recovery. These traits flourish through encouragement and cultivation across organizational development. Behavioral indicators assess an organization's resilience qualities. The organizational behavior components that lead to resistance are expanded upon and described in the 13 resilience indicators, which are classified under the primary characteristics (Resilience Expert Advisory Group 2016).

Coronavirus Pandemic Experience of SMEs

The pandemic's impact on SMEs and their response haven't been a distinct variable in resilience literature due to its evolving nature. This study introduces the "Coronavirus Pandemic Experience" as an independent variable, exploring Iranian restaurant businesses' challenges during the pandemic for insights into better organizational resilience approaches. The questionnaire addresses predicting pre-pandemic conditions, crisis responses,

bankruptcy considerations, and the absence of crisis management plans. The pandemic underscored the need for enhanced health measures, affecting operations and supply chains. Businesses adapted through reduced menus, increased takeout orders, and reevaluated interiors due to ongoing social distancing measures. According to Covid-19, restaurants are unable to remain intact. They should constantly be looking for new ways to innovate their experience, menu, and service (*Morgan 2021*). Entrepreneurs ceased their activities in the meantime; some shut down their businesses permanently. The stoppage in SME activities triggered the distraction of revenue and profits in various business segments (*Ratnasingam et al., 2020, as cited in Messabia et al. 2022*). Some studies underscore the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown experience's importance. *Neise et al. (2021)* noted that older owners or managers are more likely to exhibit resilience. This highlights the significance of prior experience in handling challenges like the pandemic. Experience is a component of resilience quality identified by *Lee, J. J. Vargo, and Seville (2013)*, encompassing the ability to respond to various disruptions, frequent risks, adaptive observation, anticipation of interruptions, and learning from experience. Tacit knowledge refers to informal on-the-job learning. Implied or merely identifiable knowledge is referred to as tacit knowledge, and it is frequently associated with intuition (*Wagner, Sujan, Sujan, Rashotte, & Sternberg, 1999, as cited in Sayegh et al. 2004*).

METHODOLOGY

Preparation and Translation of the Questionnaire and Survey Implementation

No pre-validated scales existed for Organizational Resilience (OR) in Iran's Persian language or for its hospitality industry. The survey with the items derived from HealthCheck, underwent reverse translation and was reviewed by scholars and peers for validation. The questionnaire includes sections on different aspects: questions 1-3, 6, and 7 directly relate to organizational resilience (RES), questions 4-5 assess situational awareness (SA), questions 8-9 examine network and social capital (NSC), questions 10-12 focus on employee engagement (EE), questions 11, 13-15 address decision making (DM), and questions 16-19 explore the Coronavirus pandemic experience (CPX). These sections are aligned with the HealthCheck assessment tool.

The target construct that the items related to organizational resilience in general (OR) is explained in the literature section of this study. Same applies to the items about the Coronavirus pandemic experience (CPX). The items derived from HealthCheck also includes network and social capital (NSC), employee engagement (EE) and decision making (DM) and situational awareness (SA).

Network and social capital (NSC) dimension and related items are derived from HealthCheck's 'networks and relationships' main indicator (Commonwealth of Australia, 2016), and attempts to measure the ability of the organization in identifying and minimizing the disruptive obstacles in the organization's social and human capitals, and awareness of the importance of relationships and networks of relationship with other businesses and organizations in critical or tough times.

Employee engagement (EE) items are derived from HealthCheck's 'leadership and culture' main indicator (Commonwealth of Australia, 2016) and attempts to measure the independence of employees in decision-making and rewarding them when workers solve an issue, and abundance of emphatic actions during hardship.

Decision making (DM) items are also derived from HealthCheck's 'leadership and culture' main indicator (Commonwealth of Australia, 2016) and attempts to detect whether decision-making and fast response is delegated to the workers under critical circumstances, abundance of systematically organized information and transparency of hierarchy which are considered to be important for decision making functions.

Situational awareness (SA) items are also derived from 'leadership and culture' main indicator of HealthCheck and attempts to detect the ability to identify crises in the organization.

Questions from the Australian Organizational Resilience website were translated and adjusted to be clearer for restaurant executives. Some adjustments incorporated the researcher's COVID-19 experiences. The Likert scale, ranging from 1 to 5, measured responses.

Data Collection

Data was collected from 52 restaurants in Tehran, Isfahan, and Ahwaz during the peak of the COVID-19 crisis in Iran. Over 200 questionnaires were distributed, with the majority in Tehran and fewer in Ahwaz due to its smaller population and restaurant activity. Challenges included managers' distrust and reluctance to participate. The data collection method involved a mix of convenience and snowball sampling, as the questionnaire was randomly issued. The survey implementation was performed by face to face interactions between the researcher and the restaurant owners/managers, survey's purpose and sometimes, the terminology of the questions were explained to the respondents and their responses were recorded by the researcher. The data collection began in the summer of 2020 using a 19-question survey in three Iranian cities. Due to the crisis's severity, the process faced delays and difficulties, with some restaurants declining due to conservative settings. Most responses were obtained smoothly, with additional explanations from business executives.

Data Analysis

The unique model proposed initially (which has not been presented in this study) and questionnaire faced challenges due to a lack of validation. The limited sample size prevented correlation analysis due to normal distribution prerequisites. Confirmatory factor analysis to validate the original questionnaire was also constrained by these limitations. As a result, the study confined itself to descriptive statistics and frequency analyses. A simpler statistical analysis was conducted to interpret and verify the collected data, acknowledging these limitations. **Table 2** presents the data used to interpret the findings accordingly. The columns 4 to 8 includes the frequency distribution in terms of percentages of Likert scale responses of the participants (1 to 5 options). Average scores, standard deviations and mode for each item are indicated in the following columns. However, in addition to the descriptive findings; as deliberated in the discussion section and general evaluation of the findings, the style of implementation of the survey gave the researcher opportunities of lengthy interactions with the owners/mangers, direct observation of the employees and the business and in-situ qualitative assessment of the impact of the pandemic on the restaurant businesses. The semi-qualitative nature of the interpretations will be explained in the discussion.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the Data (Ave: Average, Std.: Standart Deviation, M, mode)

Q. No.	Questions	Variables	1 %	2 %	3 %	4 %	5 %	Ave	Std	M
1	Composing and assessing a clear management program	Resilience (RES)	13.46	21.1	26.92	23.08	15.38	3.05	1.27	3
2	Vulnerability & risk management familiarity	Resilience (RES)	15.38	34.6	19.23	23.08	7.69	2.73	1.2	2
3	Behavioral & organizational preparedness in facing a crisis in business	Resilience (RES)	15.38	23.1	23.08	28.85	9.62	2.94	1.24	4
4	The organization's capability & strength towards crisis and incident within the organization or business	Situation Awareness (SA)	9.62	23.1	28.85	28.85	9.62	3.05	1.14	3, 4
5	The ability to identify the crises and symptoms before turning into challenging events	Situation Awareness (SA)	9.62	19.2	34.62	32.69	3.85	3.01	1.03	3
6	Resource allocation for dealing with crises and responding to them	Resilience (RES)	13.73	33.3	23.53	19.61	9.80	2.76	1.2	2
7	The importance of a business or organization's competitors in its survival	Resilience (RES)	9.62	17.3	21.15	23.08	28.85	3.44	1.33	5
8	Identifying and minimizing the disruptive obstacles in the organization's social and human capitals	Network and Social Capital (SC)	5.66	18.9	24.53	37.74	13.21	3.34	1.12	4
9	The importance of relationships and networks of relationship with other businesses and organizations in critical or tough times	Network and Social Capital (SC)	5.77	9.62	34.62	32.69	17.31	3.46	1.07	3
10	If workers solve an issue through their own knowledge without permission from the management and do not inflict any harm towards the organization and business, they will be rewarded	Employee Engagement (EE)	3.85	25.0	21.15	34.62	15.38	3.32	1.13	4
11	Under critical circumstances, decision-making and fast response are delegated to the workers.	Decision Making (DM)	11.54	26.9	30.77	28.85	1.92	2.82	1.04	3
12	Workers are empathic when they speak regarding potential problems with the business and the organization	Employee Engagement (EE)	3.92	27.5	39.22	15.69	13.73	3.07	1.07	3
13	Changes in the business and organization are controlled, recorded, categorized, and archived.	Decision Making (DM)	13.46	26.9	15.38	15.38	28.85	3.19	1.45	5
14	Sometimes it is unclear who becomes the ultimate and final decision-maker in a business.	Decision Making (DM)	62.75	19.6	7.84	5.88	3.92	1.68	1.1	1
15	For even a simple incident, such as a fire in the organization and business, a protocol is written, and the hierarchy is trained to follow it.	Decision Making (DM)	38.46	25.0	21.15	5.77	9.62	2.23	1.29	1
16	Before the COVID-19 pandemic, I had anticipated such conditions for the business.	Pandemic Experience (CPX)	50.00	30.7	11.54	5.77	1.92	1.78	0.99	1
17	With the onset of the COVID-19 crisis, our business faced a crisis.	Pandemic Experience	13.46	9.62	21.15	28.85	26.92	3.46	1.34	4
18	We planned to shut down our business and file for bankruptcy	Pandemic Experience	58.00	26.0	8.00	4.00	4.00	1.68	1.04	1
19	The impression is that we lack a written continuous crisis management program in such crises to prevent the closure or shutdown of a business.	Pandemic Experience (CPX)	19.23	28.8	25.00	11.54	15.38	2.75	1.32	2

FINDINGS

The findings of the survey are presented this section, in terms of the following parameters:

- Organizational Resilience (RES)
- Situational Awareness (SA)
- Network and Social Capital (NSC)
- Employee Engagement (EE)
- Decision Making (DM)
- Coronavirus Pandemic Experience (CPX)

It should be noted that only a descriptive summary and frequency analysis can be provided due to the impossibility of applying correlational or regression analysis. Such forms of analysis require a larger sample, and a validated questionnaire which was not readily available during the climax of the pandemic when this research tried to capture the situation. Furthermore, certain normality conditions were not met. The descriptive statistical data is presented in Table 2 in the data analysis section above.

RES Related Questions

Participants' responses to Likert scale questions shed light on various aspects of organizational resilience (RES). In Question #1, an average of 3.05 indicates a balanced approach to management plans. Question #2 shows modest familiarity with vulnerability management (median 2.5-3). For Question 3, a majority rated organizational readiness at 4, suggesting relative preparedness for crises. In contrast, Question 6 reveals limited crisis preparation (average 2.6). Question 7 highlights the significance of competition (average 3.5), showing Iranian restaurants prioritize competition for resilience. Overall, these questions collectively provide insights into Iranian restaurants' pandemic resilience, enhancing our understanding of their organizational resilience.

SA Related Questions

In Question 4 regarding organizational accountability during crises, participants favored the middle option (3), resulting in an average of around 3. This reflects moderate power and endurance in crisis response. Similarly, for Question 5 on crisis identification, the majority chose 3, indicating a relative ability to recognize crises. These responses together indicate moderate situational awareness, focusing on power, responsiveness, and crisis identification.

NSC Related Questions

Question 8 assessed disruptive obstacles in social and human capital (NSC). The average of 3.4, with most selecting 4, highlights the significant importance given to removing barriers within networks. In Question 9, participants rated the significance of relationships and networks during tough times (NSC) as 3.5, with a majority choosing 4. These responses underline the pivotal role of social capital and networks in enhancing organizational resilience among Iranian restaurants during the pandemic.

EE Related Questions

Question 10 delves into employee empowerment (EE), exploring their decision-making independence and rewards for autonomous issue-solving. The average of 3.4, with most choosing 4, signifies the significance of employee autonomy during crises. Question 12, also on EE, records a relative average of 3, with most picking option 3, highlighting the role of employee empathy in organizational resilience. Both questions emphasize the pivotal importance of employee empowerment in enhancing organizational resilience.

DM Related Questions

Question 11 explores decision-making and leadership (DM) competence, revealing that workers handle critical situations with a relative average of 2.8 (option 3). Question 13 examines administrative systems and recording changes, with a relative average of 3.2 favoring options 2 and 5. This underscores the relevance of office systems. Question 14 delves into hierarchy transparency, revealing a lack of clarity (average 1.7). Lastly, Question 15 assesses safety protocol adherence, with a relative average of 2.4 indicating a weaker approach. Overall, Iranian restaurant organizations exhibit relative importance in decision-making and leadership, reflecting their management knowledge and awareness.

CPX Related Questions

In Question 16, assessing the COVID-19 experience (CPX), participants showed a lack of foresight (average 1.8). Question 17 revealed that most businesses faced a crisis at the pandemic's onset (average 3.5, option 4). For Question 18, participants emphasized Iranian restaurants' endurance during the crisis (average 1.8). The final question, Question 19, addressed the absence of a comprehensive crisis management program, with an average of 2.75 indicating its lack.

Notably, the COVID-19 experience variable illustrated that high organizational resilience didn't guarantee a better pandemic experience. Conversely, a favorable experience didn't necessarily imply high organizational resilience. Gender-wise, there were 6 females and 46 males, while among participants, 28 were managers and 24 were business owners. Managers focused on Questions 13 and 19, highlighting the importance of administrative systems and crisis management programs in businesses.

Demographics

Of the participants, 6 were female and 46 were male. Out of them, 28 were managers, and 24 were business owners. Managers focused on Questions 13 and 19, emphasizing administrative systems and crisis management programs. Table 2 details participant distribution by city, role in the restaurant, and gender.

Table 3. Demographic table

CITY	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS	ROLE	GENDER
TEHRAN	25	11 of them were owners	4 of them are female
ISFAHAN	23	12 of them were owners	2 of them are female
AHWAZ	4	One of them was an owner	All of them were male
TOTAL	52		

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

General Evaluation

COVID-19 hit tourism and restaurants hard in Iran. Inadequate government support led to workforce loss, pushing activists and investors elsewhere. Poor crisis preparedness worsened the situation. From a resource-based perspective, large tourism businesses need to understand how to handle crises since they have the resources and expertise to do so (*Richie, Bentley, Cort, and Wang, 2011, as cited in Jang, Park, and Choi, 2022*).

Our data and findings suggest that limited crisis and event management knowledge, coupled with inadequate emphasis on managerial skills, contributed to business failures during crises. This lack of resilience, evident in Iranian restaurants, highlights the significance of effective management. Managing and mobilizing the organization's resources to guarantee its capability to operate throughout business-as-usual, as well as capable of supplying the additional capacity required during a crisis (*Lee, J. J. Vargo, and Seville 2013*).

Insufficient risk management and crisis awareness among managers and employees led to a lack of preparedness, post-crisis planning, and clear strategies for Iranian restaurants. Despite moderate pre-awareness, the low emphasis on risk management highlights the need for effective crisis management and defined plans to ensure resilience. Much of the information required to make good decisions is not easily accessible. There is a lot of uncertainty, a very high stock and there is a very short period working (*Lisa, Anthony, and Perrewé 2004*).

Recognizing and preparing for crises allows the allocation of resources, but research indicates inadequate resource allocation due to a lack of knowledge. While participants emphasize awareness and forecast, few emphasize resource allocation. This contradiction undermines organizational resilience, where resources are vital for effective crisis management. In particular, tourism organizations must invest in long-term capital costs for both deployable (e.g., service capacity) and intangible resources to instantly adapt to organizational crises (*Jang, Park, and Choi 2022*).

Competition among Iranian restaurants is crucial, fostering growth without weakening the organization. Acknowledged by participants, competition transforms rivals into partners, nurturing trade and strong relationships. Maintaining these alliances during crises enables shared experiences and support. Strong relationships enhance resilience, connecting competitiveness and organizational strength. Resilient entities require effective leadership, environmental awareness, vulnerability management, and adaptability. A competitive firm whose leaders are able to use their strengths to adapt, before their rivals, to quick changes in their market or industry area, implements these traits concurrently (*Lee, J. J. Vargo, and Seville 2013*).

Employee engagement boosts organizational resilience. During crises, employee compassion and camaraderie are invaluable. While some participants exhibit companionship, it's less potent than other factors due to inadequate responsiveness or discomfort within the organization. This diminishes resilience. A committed, loyal employee bolsters resilience, aiding success even in turbulent times. Resilience enables employees to challenge personal assumptions and develop advanced power by adapting to situations (*Amir and Mangundaya, 2021*).

Participants highlighted hierarchy and organizational decision-making as vital, but transparency is lacking. Despite an administrative system, Iranian restaurants face contradictions between bureaucracy, hierarchy, and decision-making, deviating from conventional definitions. The decision should also be difficult inside the framework of several players, organizational and environmental limitations, and its possible outcomes for a complete evaluation (*Huy, 1999; March 1978; Weick, 1990, as cited in Sayegh et al. 2004*).

Administrative systems and hierarchy are vital in Iranian restaurants. Sympathetic employees are more common in hierarchical setups. This system fosters competition and communication, aids crisis identification, and boosts resilience. Security protocol neglect is widespread, undermining organizations. The absence of crisis-related protocols due to managerial unfamiliarity increases risks and reduces resilience. It is desirable for organizations to educate and educate their organizational culture, protocols, and laws. Beliefs are only held by individuals, while institutions adopt beliefs in the form of doctrines, hypotheses, and protocols (*Kays 2015*).

Most participants, including business owners, lacked predictions or preparations for the COVID-19 crisis due to limited management knowledge. This absence of pre-crisis readiness is a key aspect of crisis management. Resilience, defined as restoring performance and capacity post-crisis, is hindered by this unpreparedness. However, it is also recognized that the new "normal" is likely to be created after environmental shocks (*Prideaux et al., 2003, as cited in Li et al. 2021*). Proactive activities include preparation and reduced effort in the pre-crisis period (*Li et al. 2021*).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Iranian participants initially experienced business crises. Despite lacking crisis management awareness, most chose to stay open and adapt, not opting for shutdown or bankruptcy. Their

persistence reflects a lack of self-awareness about their preparedness limitations. However, previous findings suggested that they had well-absorbed and overcome the initial shock of the crisis's onset. Organizations that better absorb shocks often experience fewer financial losses and have more sustainable systems (*DesJardine, Bansal, & Yang, 2019, as cited in Jang, Park, and Choi 2022*).

Organizational resilience in Iranian restaurants was neglected due to limited knowledge of management, risk, and crisis components. Experience and tacit knowledge have been the basis for restaurant management, relying on visual decision-making skills. There is a growing stream of literature that cites senior executives' typically implicit knowledge based on experiences (*Agor, 1986, 1990; Giunipero, Dawley, & Anthony, 1999; Kleinmuntz, 1990, as cited in Sayegh et al. 2004*). Also, this fact should not be forgotten experience teaches the incompleteness of all plans” (*Palmer, 1969, p.196, as cited in D. C. Kayes 2015*). All organizations face the fundamental problem of learning from experience because they seek careful, timely, and useful clarification of information. Resilience, and failure to adapt, overemphasis on learning costs, relying on reasonable decision-making, and limited definitions of what constitutes success challenge learning in the contemporary organization (*D. C. Kayes 2015*).

High organizational resilience didn't always correlate with better Crisis Preparedness Index (CPX) among participants. Improved CPX didn't necessarily signify higher resilience. Iranian restaurant data showed that crisis response strength didn't directly lead to bankruptcy, and bankruptcy didn't mean a lack of crisis response power. Tolerance increases diminished bankruptcy decisions. Restaurants identifying crises stayed afloat during COVID-19 despite challenges. Sympathetic leadership and empathetic employees enhance crisis prediction. Some had better experiences, but CPX's relationship with Net Sympathy Capabilities (NSC) was inconclusive. Decisiveness showed mixed results, indicating decisions didn't uniformly enhance CPX.

Comparison with other studies

Comparing this study with German (*Neise et al. 2021*) and Chinese (*Li et al. 2021*) studies on restaurant industry resilience, Chinese restaurants swiftly closed due to government measures, curbing COVID-19 spread. Chinese efficiency reduced infections but affected performance. Iranian restaurants faced challenges in crisis response. Chinese restaurants reacted effectively, benefiting resilience. Short-term responses aid resilience (*Neise et al. 2021*). Chinese resilience is tied to strong social capital and networks, enhancing competitiveness. Company social responsibility (CSR) is a well-studied example of how a company's actions in the market or community can have a positive effect on a firm's competitiveness by lowering costs (*Aguilera et al. 2007, as cited in Li et al. 2021*) and influencing employee and customer loyalty (*Ding and Jiang 2021, as cited in Li et al. 2021*). Chinese restaurants outperformed Iranians and Germans in long-term, strategic response, and decision-making. They revamped service operations, focusing on food delivery, kitchens, cooking methods, ingredients, menus, and staff training. Prioritizing cost savings enabled resilience and financial stability. The initiative was implemented, including a temporary closure, wage reduction, reduction of raw materials, and other operating costs (*Li et al. 2021*). In the fields of leadership, hierarchy, and decision-making, the Chinese have generally performed better. Not to mention that they set up a huge strategic recovery plan for the industry. The Chinese administration has supplied commercial financial aid for small and medium-sized companies, and 95 per cent of China's food and beverage industry was included in these projects (*Cheng, 2020, as cited in Li et al. 2021*). Various health and safety methods have been adopted by restaurants, including manipulation, wearing gloves and masks, customer body temperature checks, staff body temperature checks, and environmental disinfection (*Li et al. 2021*). In Germany, *Neise et al.* stated that the industry faced serious problems with the onset of COVID-19; however, they already had serious financial problems prior to the pandemic. In terms of responding to the crisis, it was evident that German restaurants showed a positive reaction. The results demonstrate that short-term responses are advantageous for enterprise resilience (*Neise et al. 2021*). Similar to Iranian restaurants, owners in Germany were less expected to be noticed as resilient; as it has been observed in this study, managers paid more attention to questions that focused on managerial knowledge.

Quantitative or Qualitative

The study was survey-based research, but the researcher had met all the managers/owners of the restaurants where the surveys were conducted. Most of the time the researcher read the questions and explained the questions occasionally. The researcher had the chance to observe temporary employees, the environment and of course the context personally. This provided some kind of tacit intuition about the context and quality of the management in general. So, this raises the question of whether research similar to this scope should have a systematically more qualitative dimension in terms of methodology.

Future Research

This research was a cross-sectional study capturing the business trends of Iranian restaurants during a defined period of the pandemic. For further studies, the longitudinal studies can be prioritized, as these studies of the Iranian restaurants can result in an in-depth understanding and more accurate analysis, in comparison to their statistical community. As there was no strong financial backing for the project, there was a limitation for the selected target community. Our suggestion for further studies and research is to allocate more financial resources, public funding. Given the intense environment of the Iranian government, assistance from governmental contributions, in getting the necessary clearance for information collection and commute could be facilitating. The Survey development needs to be completed by revising and improving the items, and going through confirmatory and exploratory factor analysis with new data collection and a sufficient sample size to complete the proper adaptation to the Iranian context.

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